

Fukuoka Method: A Sustainable Natural Way of Farming

Paper Id : 19628 Submission Date : 2025-01-05 Acceptance Date : 2025-01-22 Publication Date : 2025-01-25

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.14884190

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Abstract The conventional farming has revolutionized food production and transformed the Indian agriculture from subsistence to a surplus generating enterprise. Now, there is a need for exploring alternative agricultural systems that are more sustainable. Today agriculture and food system undoubtedly face challenges from climate change to environmental degradation. Fukuoka or Natural farming is a sustainable agricultural method. It is a chemical free, agro based farming system involving livestock integrated natural farming methods along with diversified crop systems. It relies upon crop rotation, use of crop residue, animal manures, legumes and green manures. Natural Farming if done effectively enhances soil fertility, environmental and human health, along with reduction in environmental degradation. It emphasizes chemical-free or minimal intervention methods to enhance soil biological fertility without relying on external inputs. There is an urgent need to increase the natural food production to feed the increasing population. Climate change is considered a major threat to agricultural production affecting the crops' productivity and environment. After the COVID pandemic, the concern regarding the human health became an important issue.

Keywords Sustainable Agriculture, Fukuoka or Natural Farming, Zero Budget Farming.

Introduction Natural farming, also known as the Fukuoka Method, is a chemical-free farming system that integrates crops, trees, and livestock, established and popularised by Mr. Masanobu Fukuoka, a Japanese farmer and a philosopher. This farming method (the Fukuoka Method), is also known as "the natural way of farming", or "do-nothing farming". Natural farming prioritizes soil and ecosystem health, aiming to reduce input costs while improving farm health and crop yields. Natural farming allows for a wide range of agroecological practices - composting, mulching, green manuring, crop rotations, intercropping, livestock integration - and takes a holistic approach to farming systems.

A report from NITI Aayog says that natural farming is the need of the hour as the cost of production of food grains has escalated drastically due to increased cost of agricultural inputs viz., chemical fertilizers, pesticides, fungicides and herbicides. Besides, it is the best way to restore degraded lands, enhance soil health, conserve water and reduce the usage of chemical inputs while improving the nutritional quality of crops and supporting the local food systems. Numerous studies have shown that natural farming is more productive, sustainable, water efficient, and better for the ecology of farms and the soil.

Objective of study This paper is an attempt to focus on comprehensive outlook for sustainable complementary farming practice namely natural farming and zero budget farming.

Review of Literature According to Mishra 2013, 'Natural Farming' or 'Eco-Agriculture' or 'Ecofriendly Agriculture' is suggested as a neoteric approach to improve both traditional and modern agricultural practices, which aims to safeguard the environment, public health, and communities. Devarinti, 2016; Tiwari & Raj, 2020 regarded natural farming as a profitable agricultural method with the potential to boost employment and rural development. De 2022 in his study considers natural farming as a chemical free traditional agro-ecology based diversified farming system which integrates crops, trees and livestock with functional biodiversity which increases the production, saves water and improves soil health. Sarangi et.al 2023 discussed natural farming as a concept of chemical free diversified agriculture-based farming practices with more concern on affordable native

resources and management practices in which use of externally purchased inputs is avoided or minimised and use of native resources with agro-ecological principles, people participation and common resource management is largely focused for the benefit of farmers and community. Biswas and Pakhira 2023, concluded that the natural farming presents a possible alternative to traditional farming as farmers deal with issues like diminishing soil fertility, water shortage and environmental degradation

Main Text Key principles of Fukuoka/Natural Farming

1. Adopts the philosophy of "Work in harmony with nature"
2. Neither chemical nor organic fertilizers are added to the soil(only decomposition of organic matter)
3. Multi-cropping is encouraged over a single crop method
4. Relies on natural processes without using any external inputs
5. Soil fertility is maintained through natural processes like mulching, microbial activity and cover crop
6. Economic viability

Government Initiatives in India

The Government of India has launched the National Mission on Natural Farming (NMNF) to promote natural farming in mission mode across the country as a standalone Centrally Sponsored Scheme under the Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers' Welfare. Rooted in the traditional knowledge inherited from their forefathers, farmers will practise Natural Farming (NF) as a chemical free farming which involves local livestock integrated natural farming methods, diversified crop systems, etc. NMNF aims at promoting NF practices for providing safe & nutritious food for all. The Mission is designed to support farmers to reduce input cost of cultivation and dependency to externally purchased inputs. Natural farming will build & maintain healthy soil ecosystems, promote biodiversity and encourage diverse cropping systems to enhance resilience as suitable to the local agroecology are the benefits of natural farming. As of 2023, it is estimated that about 4.09 lakh hectares of land in India are under natural farming and total fund of Rs. 4587.17 lakh has been released in 8 States across the country namely Andhra Pradesh (1.00 lakh hectares), Madhya Pradesh (0.99 lakh hectares), Chhattisgarh (0.85 lakh hectares), Kerala (0.84 lakh hectares), Odisha (0.24 lakh hectares), Himachal Pradesh (0.12 lakh hectares), Jharkhand (0.034 lakh hectares), Tamil Nadu (0.02 lakh hectares). The National Institute of Agricultural Extension Management (MANAGE), Hyderabad is the Nodal agency for promotion of natural farming in the country.

Natural Farming Status in the State of Rajasthan

Government of Rajasthan has been promoting Natural Farming since 2019-20 as a pilot project. According to NITI AYOJ, YEAR 2019-20: Honorable Chief Minister of Rajasthan during the budget speech of FY2019-20 declared support to natural farming to reduce input costs with a view to empower farmers through remunerative agriculture – Kheti Mein Jaan Toh Sashakt Kisan. The scheme in the form of a pilot project was initiated in three districts of the State viz. Tonk, Sirohi and Banswada.

YEAR 2020-21: The scheme was implemented in 15 districts of the State viz. Tonk, Ajmer, Alwar, Baran, Jhalawad, Bheelwada, Udaipur, Baanswad, Seeker, Nahaur, Baadmer, Churu, Jaisalmer, Hanumangadh and Sirohi. Under the scheme, 17,900 farmers were trained on natural farming.

YEAR 2021-22: 750 Village Panchayats have been selected in 15 districts for implementing the scheme during FY2021-22 and a provision of expenditure of Rs 200 Lakhs has been made.

Present scenario -

1. Farmers are cultivating green gram, black gram, maize, pearl millet, soybean and groundnut along with vegetables on 8,000 ha of land in Tonk, Sirohi and Banswada under the scheme initiated in 2019-20.
2. Farmers interested in natural farming have been provided with primary information about the advantages of natural farming along with the disadvantages of using chemical fertilizers and insecticides. The farmers have also been taught low-cost farming techniques, production techniques and the use of yathajivamrit, beejamrit, ghanamrit, etc. at the local level.

Zero Budget Natural Farming (ZBNF) is a farming technique that aims to increase farmers' revenue by growing crops without the use of chemicals and pesticides. Subhash

Palekar, an Indian agriculturist and Padma Shri recipient, developed Zero Budget Natural Farming (ZBNF) in the mid-1990s. ZBNF is a chemical-free farming method that uses low-cost, locally-sourced ingredients to raise crops. Palekar is also known as the "Father of Natural Farming in India" The Rajasthan state government started a scheme for ZBNF in 2020-2021. It is based on Jivamitra (mixture of fresh desi cow dung and urine), Bijamitra (local cow dung), Acchadana (mulching) and Whapasa (moisture) The scheme is now known as Bhartiya Prakritik Krishi Padhati (BPKP) and is a sub-scheme of the Paramparagat Krishi Vikas Yojana (PKVY). The ZBNF system was developed to reduce the demand for chemical fertilizers and pesticides, which can harm the environment, soil, and human health.

Broader impacts of natural farming

1. The adoption of natural farming extends beyond agriculture influencing environmental sustainability. Key impacts are:
2. Improved soil health and biodiversity
3. Reduction in health risks and increase in health benefits
4. Environment friendly as techniques like mulching and no till farming reduces carbon emission
5. With practices like mulching and no-till farming, there's a significant reduction in water evaporation, promoting efficient water use
6. Diversified cropping system and lower production costs ensure steady food supplies and economic stability for farmers
7. With increasing concerns about environmental degradation, natural farming is essential to maintain and restore ecological balance by prioritizing biodiversity and healthy ecosystems
8. Natural farming emphasizes on sustainable agriculture
9. It often integrates indigenous knowledge and practices, ensuring the preservation and continuation of invaluable traditional wisdom
10. As the demand for natural farming grows, there is increasing research on refining techniques, discovering new practices, and integrating traditional knowledge with the modern science.

Conclusion Challenges and A Way Out

1. Lack of awareness among farmers regarding farming techniques
2. Competition to conventional farmers who uses synthetic fertilizers and pesticides to produce larger quantities of crops and livestock
3. Natural farming may require more labour than traditional farming
4. There may be limited training and awareness programs, and the procedures for subsidies and loans may be difficult.
5. Agricultural marketing can be challenging in finding buyers, negotiating prices, and transporting goods

Natural Farming practices is easy and can be done on any scale. It offers a wide solution to various problems, such as food insecurity, farmers' distress, and health problems arising due to pesticide and fertilizer residue in food and water, global warming, climate change and natural calamities. Education and awareness can promote sustainable agriculture methods and encourage people to adopt natural farming methods.

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